

Extraction of Zinc(II) as Chloride by High Molecular Weight Amine, Amberlite LA-1

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A rapid and selective method for the extraction of milligram amounts of Zn(II) from hydrochloric acid solution with liquid anion exchanger, Amberlite LA-1, in nitrobenzene has been proposed. Quantitative extraction has been achieved in the hydrochloric acid conc. range 2-4 M. Diluents having high dielectric constant values show improved extraction results, compared to benzene, xylene, toluene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. The effect of such variables as hydrochloric acid conc., contact time, stripping time and extractant conc. was studied and the effect of foreign ions investigated. The separation of zinc from several synthetic mixtures is also found quantitative. The probable composition of the extracted species has been deduced from the extraction data.

IN recent years, solvent extraction with high molecular weight amines and quaternary ammonium compounds has been extensively used as a promising technique in industries and atomic energy programmes. The applications include the removal of toxic elements such as Hg, As, Cd, Zn, Cu, Pb, Cr etc. for pollution abatement from industrial effluents and recovery of fertile and fissionable materials from irradiated fuel elements at atomic energy centres.

The amines, due to their unique anion exchange ability, extract anionic metal complexes from the aqueous phase. Separation and estimation of such type of metals through liquid cation exchangers have been carried out in this laboratory¹⁻⁵. The liquid anion exchanger, on the other hand, is the point of interest to explore in the extraction of toxic metals. The present work reports on the selectivity of Amberlite LA-1 for the extraction of zinc(II) chloro-complex. No such work is reported in the literature⁶⁻⁹.

The mechanism of extraction of zinc from aqueous hydrochloric acid solution with the secondary amine, pretreated with hydrochloric acid, is of this type :

where o=organic phase and a=aqueous phase.

The secondary amine and its salt with anionic chloro-complex of zinc are essentially insoluble in aqueous solutions but exhibit high solubility in organic solvents.

Experimental

Apparatus: A single pan balance, SICO Popular Model, Scientific Instrument Co., Calcutta was used for taking weights. Separatory funnels (150 ml) were used for extraction experiments.

Reagents :

The liquid anion exchanger, Amberlite LA-1, manufactured by the Rohm and Haas Co., Philadelphia, USA, and supplied by B.D.H., Poole, England was used without further purification. Nitrobenzene (Sarabhai M. Chemicals, GR) was used as diluent. The amine was suitably diluted with nitrobenzene and converted to its chloride form by equilibrating with hydrochloric acid for 5 min. The molar concentration of the amine was determined by stripping the chloride by sodium hydroxide solution and then titrating the chloride with standard silver nitrate solution using potassium chromate as indicator^{6,10}.

ZnSO₄·7H₂O (B.D.H., A.R.) was used for analysis. A stock solution of zinc (6.5 mg/ml) was prepared in double deionised water and the solution standardized by complexometric titration with EDTA (disodium salt) using xylenol orange as an indicator¹¹.

The chemicals and solvents used were all of analytical grade unless otherwise mentioned.

General extraction procedure :

The procedure was based on solvent extraction technique. The ratio of the volumes of aqueous phase and the organic phase was maintained at 1 : 1. In a separatory funnel, the aqueous phase was made up from a portion of the solution containing 6.5 mg of zinc. Standard hydrochloric acid was added to maintain the required acid strength. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 10 ml. The aqueous phase was equilibrated with 10 ml of 5% v/v Amberlite in nitrobenzene (amine : nitrobenzene = 1 : 20 by volume) for 5 min. The equilibration time was varied from 1-10 min and it was found that the distribution coefficient reached a constant value within 2 min. However, the equilibration time was fixed at 5 min. All the experiments were carried out at 27 ± 1°. The two layers were

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allowed to settle for 10-15 min. The organic phase was then separated carefully to another separatory funnel. The aqueous phase was collected, the excess acid was neutralised by ammonia solution and the amount of zinc present in the aqueous phase was determined by EDTA titration. Then, 10 ml of 2M nitric acid solution was added to the organic phase and the mixture was shaken for 5 min. The two phases were allowed to settle, the organic phase was separated carefully and the corresponding aqueous phase (acid extract) was collected and neutralised by ammonia solution. The amount of zinc extracted in that phase was determined.

Results and Discussion

Hydrochloric acid concentration :

The extraction behaviour of zinc(II) with Amberlite LA-1 at various acid concentrations is given in Fig. 1. The experiments were performed with constant extractant concentration (5% v/v) and constant

Fig. 1. Extraction of Zn(II) with Amberlite LA-1 as a function of [HCl] in molarity.

metal concentration ($9.9 \times 10^{-3} M$). The extraction of zinc increases with increased hydrochloric acid concentration and becomes quantitative at 2M and onwards. The optimum hydrochloric acid range for quantitative extraction is therefore from 2M onwards. The distribution ratio was calculated from the extraction data using the relation

$$D = \frac{V}{V'} \left(\frac{100}{100-x} - 1 \right)$$

where V and V' are the respective volumes of the aqueous and organic phases, respectively and x is the percentage of zinc extracted^{2,3}.

In order to evaluate the probable reaction mechanism of Zn(II) with chloride ion, the extraction, at constant ionic strength (2.3M), was carried out with varying amount of hydrochloric acid. Sodium sulphate was used to maintain the constant ionic strength. Plot of log D against log [Cl] produces a straight line (Fig. 2) with a slope of 2.1 indicating the formation of $(ZnCl_4)^{2-}$ in the aqueous phase. At lower chloride concentration the formation of $(ZnCl_3)^-$ is also expected. Therefore, the

reaction in the aqueous phase is proposed to be :

Fig. 2. Plot of log D against log [Cl] at constant [amine].

Amberlite LA-1 concentration :

At constant concentration of zinc ($9.9 \times 10^{-3} M$) and hydrochloric acid (2M), the extraction of zinc as a function of Amberlite LA-1 concentration in nitrobenzene was carried out. The extraction of zinc is quantitative provided the secondary amine : zinc molar ratio is ≥ 2 . Plot of log D against log [Amberlite LA-1] produces a straight line (Fig. 3) with slope 2. Hence the extraction mechanism of

Fig. 3. Plot of log D against log [Amberlite LA-1] at 2M HCl.

zinc(II) is proposed to be :

The zinc(II) : Amberlite LA-1 ratio in the extracted species is therefore 1 : 2.

Diluents :

Zinc was extracted with 5% Amberlite LA-1 solution in various diluents (Table 1). The results indicate quantitative extraction of zinc with nitrobenzene which has a high dielectric constant. But the extraction of zinc in benzene (a diluent of low dielectric constant) is more than that in other diluents of high dielectric constant. Hence a clear conclusion cannot be drawn for the diluents used for extraction. The dielectric constant is not the only factor involved.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DILUENTS ON EXTRACTION OF ZINC

Diluents	Dielectric constant	Metal extracted (%)	Distribution ratio (D _{Zn})
n-Hexane	1.9	66.5	2.0
Carbon tetrachloride	2.2	30.6	0.4
Benzene	2.3	79.8	3.9
Xylene	2.4	75.7	3.1
Toluene	2.4	53.2	1.1
Chloroform	4.8	15.7	0.1
Butanol	16.1	59.0	1.4
Nitrobenzene	35.7	97.7	41.7

Equilibration time and stripping time :

The contact time was varied from 1 to 10 min. The distribution ratio reached a constant value after 2 min of shaking and back extraction was complete within 5 min. Therefore, the optimum equilibration period was chosen as 5 min in all the experiments.

Metal ion concentration :

Loading experiments, at constant concentration of both amine and hydrochloric acid, were carried out by varying amounts of zinc. More than 96.5% of zinc was extracted from 0.065 to 1.30 g/l under optimum extraction conditions. Fig. 4 shows

plot of $\log [Zn^{2+}]_0$ against $\log [Zn^{2+}]_a$. The ratio of metal to amine concentration in organic phase is found to be 1 : 2 which again supports the proposed extracted species as $[(R_2NH_2)_2(ZnCl_4)_a]_0$.

Extractive separations :

The effect of diverse ions on the quantitative extraction of Zn(II) at optimum condition is shown in Table 2. The metal ions like mercury, cadmium, lead, iron, bismuth and copper are coextracted. The tolerance limits for such ions as cobalt, aluminium, chromium, fluoride and iodide are low (shown in Table 2). Above these limits extraction decreases. Calcium, strontium, barium, magnesium, manganese, nickel, sulphate, phosphate and bromide do not interfere with the extraction of zinc.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE EXTRACTION OF Zn(II) WITH AMBERLITE LA-1 [Zinc(II) 6.5 mg ; HCl] 2 M

Diverse ions	Amount added	Source	Zinc extracted (%)
Ca ²⁺	350 mg	CaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	97.4
*Sr ²⁺	350 mg	SrCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	97.4
*Ba ²⁺	350 mg	BaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	97.4
Mg ²⁺	200 mg	MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	97.6
Mn ²⁺	150 mg	MnCl ₂ .4H ₂ O	97.4
Ni ²⁺	120 mg	NiSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	96.5
Co ²⁺	15 mg	CoSO ₄ .6H ₂ O	96.5
Al ³⁺	5 mg	Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	96.0
Cr ³⁺	2 mg	Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ .6H ₂ O	97.4
SO ₄ ²⁻	800 mg	MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	97.4
PO ₄ ³⁻	450 mg	Na ₂ HPO ₄	96.5
Br ⁻	250 mg	KBr	96.5
F ⁻	40 mg	NH ₄ HF	96.0
I ⁻	20 mg	KI	96.0

* Zn(OAC)₂ was used instead of ZnSO₄.

Separation of zinc from synthetic mixtures :

Quantitative separation of zinc from some synthetic mixtures was attempted and the results are shown in Table 3. Figures in parenthesis against an ion indicate the amount of the ion present in milligrams.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log [Zn^{2+}]_0$ vs $\log [Zn^{2+}]_a$.

TABLE 3—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF ZINC(II) FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES USING AMBERLITE LA-1

Sample No.	[Zinc(II) 6.5 mg ; [HCl] 2M] Mixture taken (mg)	Zinc extracted (%)
*1.	Ca ²⁺ (175) + Sr ²⁺ (175)	96.5
*2.	Ca ²⁺ (175) + Ba ²⁺ (175)	98.6
3.	Ca ²⁺ (175) + Mg ²⁺ (100)	96.5
*4.	Ba ²⁺ (175) + Sr ²⁺ (150)	98.0
5.	Mn ²⁺ (50) + Ni ²⁺ (50)	97.4
6.	Mn ²⁺ (60) + Co ²⁺ (8)	96.5
7.	Mn ²⁺ (60) + Al ³⁺ (2)	97.4
8.	Ni ²⁺ (50) + Co ²⁺ (8)	97.4
*9.	Ca ²⁺ (100) + Sr ²⁺ (100) + Ba ²⁺ (100)	97.4
10.	Mn ²⁺ (20) + Ni ²⁺ (20) + Co ²⁺ (5)	96.5
11.	Mn ²⁺ (15) + Ni ²⁺ (15) + Al ³⁺ (2)	96.0
12.	Ni ²⁺ (10) + Co ²⁺ (5) + Al ³⁺ (2)	96.0

* Zn(OAC)₂ was used instead of ZnSO₄.

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Acknowledgement

One of the authors (N. P.) is grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Fellowship and also to the Principal, U. N. College, Soro, Orissa for study leave.